

The controversial appropriation of the Mona Lisa by King Francis I and its consequences with regard to the potential claim of ownership of the painting by the descendants of Leonardo da Vinci

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When Leonardo da Vinci had finished the portrait of the *Mona Lisa*, he was certainly far from imagining that when he died King Francis I would monopolize it by using the right of windfall and that his disciple Francisco Melzi would get his hands on his other paintings, after having probably forged a forgery of letters and an apocryphal will. He was even further from suspecting that his portrait would become the most expensive and famous in the world, protected under armored glass in a museum visited every year by millions of people from all over the world. He could not have imagined that five centuries later the story of this portrait would resurface before the highest French administrative court in order to restore not only what is right in the face of the monarch's arbitrariness with regard to the legality of the Louvre Museum's collections, but also in the face of the inheritance rights of his descendants.¹

The circumstances of the appropriation of the painting

The Louvre Museum exhibits in its painting department the portrait of Lisa Gherardini, wife of Francesco del Giocondo, known as the Mona Lisa or

Mona Lisa painted by Leonardo di ser Piero da Vinci, known as Leonardo da Vinci.

The artist, who was pensioned and lodged by the king at the manor of Cloux (now the Clos Lucé), near Amboise, and above all the legend that made him die in the arms of the sovereign, led us to believe that the Mona Lisa had been acquired by the king for hard cash, or even offered to the latter.

The greatest doubts exist as to the conditions under which Francis I came into possession of the painting. It is likely that the painting was incorporated into the private domain of the Crown under the right of windfall.

It appears that in order to be able to dispose of his property and escape the right of windfall, this old sovereign right by virtue of which the property of a childless foreigner dying in France fell ipso facto into the hand of the king, Leonardo da Vinci, should have obtained a letter of naturality from Francis I.

Under the Ancien Régime, the foreigner was distinguished from the "*French natural*" by his birth outside the kingdom. At that time, jus soli was the necessary condition for being recognized as French from birth.

Through this definition, it must be understood that a person born of foreign parents in the kingdom of France is considered to be French.

On the other hand, a person born of French parents in another country cannot claim to be French. The status of foreigner imposes a certain number of constraints and makes the foreigner a godsend. Laurent Bouchel, a jurist of the early seventeenth century, says in this regard: "*the right of windfall was introduced in France [...] to know him who was born in the kingdom and who was not born of it, yet came to dwell there, and to differentiate between the one and the other.*"²

The aubain, at the legal level, is marked by the impossibility of passing on one's property to one's heirs.

The only way for him to escape these constraints is

action to obtain its restitution".

Decision published on the arianeweb database of the website of the Council of State <https://conseil-etat.fr> – Conclusions of the public rapporteur Laurent Domingo. This judgment is currently the subject of an appeal. before the European Court of Human Rights.

² "*The General Customs of the Baillage of Senlis*" by Laurent Bouchel, Lawyer at the Parliament of Paris (1601 – Editions Rolé Boutonnet)

¹ The French Council of State has been seized of a request for a declaration of non-existence of the decision taken by King François 1st to appropriate the Mona Lisa under the right of windfall and a request for removal from the inventory of the Louvre Museum on behalf of Leonardo da Vinci's descendants. In decision no. 491862 of 14 May 2024 (10th chamber), the Council of State declared this request inadmissible and decided that "*only the legitimate owners had an interest, if necessary, in bringing legal*

to become a French citizen.

The first letters of naturality appeared in the fourteenth century, sometimes under the name of "*letters of bourgeoisie*". A distinction must be made between the letter of naturality itself, sealed in the form of a charter (green wax on red and green silk laces), and the letter of declaration of naturality (sealed with yellow wax on a double tail). While the former gives a foreigner the status of regnicole, the latter is in fact only the recognition of the applicant's status as regnicole and does not change his status. The postulant had to make a request to the royal chancellery.

After obtaining the letters, the beneficiary had a period of one year to have them verified by the Chamber of Accounts and registered by the Chamber of the Treasury, otherwise they would have lapsed. He had them, if he wished, registered by other courts (parliaments, bailiwicks and seneschals), but this was not compulsory³.

Leonardo da Vinci was born in the town of Vinci in Tuscany on the night of Friday, April 14, 1452, between nine and half past ten in the evening. The child was the result of an illegitimate love affair between Messer Piero Fruosino di Antonio da Vinci, a 25-year-old notary, and a 22-year-old woman named Caterina di Meo Lippi, the daughter of small farmers, born in 1436 and orphaned at the age of 14. Leonardo's father was married five times. From the last two marriages came ten half-brothers and two half-sisters.

Leonardo da Vinci had two faithful disciples who assisted him and with whom he had a very "close" relationship:

- Gian Giacomo Caprotti da Oreno, dit Salaï
- Francesco Melzi

Leonardo da Vinci died on 2 May 1519. A few weeks after the death, Francesco Melzi sent a letter dated 15 June 1519 to the artist's living brothers⁴, which reads as follows:

"I think you know the death of Master Leonardo, your brother and to me as the best of fathers. It would be

impossible for me to express the sorrow I felt for it, and as long as my limbs stand together, I shall retain a perpetual misfortune, and that with good reason, because he had a very devoted and ardent love for me every day. Everyone has lamented the loss of such a man, who no longer has the possession of life. May Almighty God give him eternal rest. He came out of the present life on the second day of May with all the sacraments of Holy Mother Church, and well prepared. As he had letters from the most Christian king allowing him to make a will and bequeath what belonged to him to whomever he pleased, and that without eredes supplicantis sint regnicolae⁵, without these letters he could not make a valid will, and all would have been lost, which is the custom here, at least for what is possessed in this country, the said Master Leonardo has made a will, which I would have sent you if I had had a reliable person.

I am waiting for an uncle of mine to come here, who will then return to Milan; I will give it to him, and he will be a good intermediary, having no other means. As for what concerns you in this will, if there is no other, the said Master Leonardo possesses at Sanla-Maria Nuova in the hands of the Camerlengo, who has signed and numbered the acknowledgments, 400 écus au soleil, which are at 5 per cent; On October 16, six years will have passed. There is also mention of a property in Fiesole, which he wants to be divided between you. The will does not contain anything else that concerns you. I will please⁶, if not that I offer you all that I am worth and all that I can, putting all my zeal and all my desire at the disposal of your will, with the continuity of my compliments.

Written at Amboise on the first day of June, 1519.

Give me an answer by the Pondi

Like your brother

Francisco MELZI"

The content of this letter is questionable, to say the least.

The highly suspicious content of Francisco Melzi's letter of June 1, 1519 and the alleged

³ "*Dictionnaire de l'Ancien Régime*", under the direction of Lucien Bély, Paris, PUF, 1996 - article "*Étrangers en France*" by Jean-François Dubost

⁴ "*Le testament de Léonard de Vinci*"- Réunion des sociétés des Beaux-Arts en 1893, 17th session, Paris, Plon,

1893, p.780-800

⁵ "*eredes supplicantis sint regnicolae*": without the heirs of the supplicant being regnicoles

⁶ "*Nec plura*": I won't tell you more

will signed by Leonardo da Vinci

First of all, Francisco Melzi took great care to remind Leonardo da Vinci's brothers of the application of the rules of succession applicable to foreigners, insisting on the fact that he had obtained letters of naturality from King Francis I, without which no will would have been valid.

It is very surprising that Francisco Melzi draws attention to this purely legal detail. And this is all the more so since he specifies that he cannot send this will to Leonardo da Vinci's brothers, because he does not have a reliable person... He adds that he is waiting for a visit from one of his uncles to whom he will give the will so that he can act as an intermediary... He went on to inform the brothers that the will included clauses relating to a sum of money of 400 crowns and a property in Fiseole. And nothing else about them.

However, according to Francisco Melzi, no trace of a letter of naturality granted by Francis 1st to Leonardo da Vinci has ever been found, let alone verified by the Chamber of Accounts or registered with the Chamber of the Treasury within the period of one year. The Imprimerie Nationale, on the initiative of the Academy of Moral and Political Sciences, has published, in the collection of ordinances of the kings of France, the catalogue of the acts of Francis I. This exhaustive catalogue includes 9 volumes that reproduce the acts of the reign of François 1st between 1515 and 1547⁷. This document contains all the letters of naturality granted.

A systematic search has not found the slightest trace of any letter of naturality concerning Leonardo da Vinci. Research at the National Archives has also been unsuccessful.

Historian Bertrand Jestaz⁸ reports that *"this will is known in the form of a copy or rather a translation preserved in the archives of the Melzi family"*.

Indeed, the original deed supposed to have been executed before the notary of Amboise Guillaume Boreau should necessarily have been written in

French. This original has never been found.

It is a simple translation into Italian (sic) that would have been discovered in the archives of the Melzi family, although the original, which cannot be found anywhere, should have been passed in French before the notary of Amboise.

In his aforementioned article *"The Testament of Leonardo da Vinci"*, the historian Anatole de Montaiglon gives us the following very interesting details on the circumstances of the exhumation of the translation of the copy of the alleged will:

"As it was passed by a notary of Amboise, or rather by the notary of Amboise, and as the office, from the end of the fifteenth century to the present day, has remained in the same family and has kept the same name, it is needless to say that it was in its interest to continue it and to find the original minute there. As in the published text there is only a question of legacies to Italians, Leonardo, who was a natural son and who was brought up with care by his father, who was later married, was always on good terms with his family, it was possible that what had been sent to Milan was only an extract and only what was necessary in Italy. The production of the will took the very source was therefore very desirable, and it was not failed to be attempted, very uselessly, although those who applied to the right door had every right to see it open before them.

But M. l'Abbé Chevalier, the historian of Chenonceaux and the author of the book on the Communal Archives of Amboise, M. Charles de Grandmaison, the learned archivist of the department of Indre-et-Loire and the author of the History of Arts in Touraine, I myself, with the highest and apparently most certain introductions, were as politely as equally rejected by a rejection. The old part of the documents of the study was not yet in order; the move was imminent, only then could they be classified, then it would be with the greatest pleasure that, if we met the blessed room, etc. We have taken it for granted. When the notarial dynasty of the Boreaus, which had hitherto lived from male to male for three centuries, ceased in 1885, and the office necessarily changed its name, one of the clerks of the new notary, M. C. Martin, was able to put his hand in the old

⁷ *"Catalogue des actes de François"* 1st compiled by Paul Marichal, Paul (1870-1943), volumes 1 to 9 – Bibliothèque Nationale de France.

⁸ *"François 1er, Salai et les tableaux de Léonard"* - Revue de l'Art, 1999, n°126. pp. 68-72. See also P. Richter, *"The literary works of Leonardo da Vinci"*, London, 1883, II,

pp. 468-471, or L. Beltrami, note 1, no. 244, pp. 152-154.

"Documenti e memorie riguardanti la vita e le opere di Leonardo da Vinci", Milan, 1919, no. 245 p. 155, after the edition in the *"Ritratti ed elogi di uomini illustri toscani"*, Lucca, 1771. II).

paperwork hitherto locked up in barrels, which is in no way strange and unusual; de Thou, the great historian of the sixteenth century, tells us that, among his sources of information, he counts the pamphlets, pamphlets, and loose sheets which he had carefully collected and preserved in barrels, he found there, not the original minute, but an old copy on paper of the seventeenth century, evidently made on account of the curiosity and exceptional importance of the document. He communicated it to M. Scribe, the professor of drawing at the college of Romorantin; it is to M. Scribe that the meeting of the Congress of the Societies of Fine Arts owes the important communication. We now know that the old minute-books of the sixteenth century will not be found and that the original piece is irrevocably lost."

Anatole de Montaignon continues by giving us the text reproduced below relating to the French translation of the copy written in Italian when the original, which cannot be found, should have been written in French...

"TRANSLATION

Let it be manifest to everyone, present and future, that at the Court of the King our Lord at Amboise, before us personally constituted Messire Leonardo da Vinci, Painter to the King, here present, residing at the place called Le Cloux, near Amboise, who, considering the certainty of death and the uncertainty of his hour, has acknowledged and confessed before us in the said Court, to which he has submitted and submits the following:

To have made and ordered, by the contents of this present, his will and the order of his last will and testament in the following manner.

First of all, he commends his soul to God our Lord, to the glorious Virgin Mary, to Monsignor Saint Michael and to all the blessed angels and saints of Paradise.

Item, the Testator wishes to be buried in the church of Saint-Florentin d'Amboise and that his body be carried there by the Capuchins of this church.

Item, that his body be accompanied from the said place to the church of Saint-Florentin by the College of the said church, namely the Rector and the Prior or the Vicars and Priests of the church of Saint-Denis d'Amboise and with them the Friars Minor of the said place, and, before his body is carried to the said church, the said testator desires that three great masses be

celebrated in the said church of Saint-Florentin with Deacon and Subdeacon; that on the same day that the three great masses aforesaid shall be said, thirty more low masses of St. Gregory shall be said.

Item, that in the said church of Saint-Denis the same Service be celebrated as above.

Item, that in the church of the said Friars and Minor Religious the same Service be celebrated.

Item the aforesaid testator gives and grants to Messire François de Melzo, Gentleman of Milan, as a reward for the gracious services rendered by him in the past, all and every one of the books which the said testator now possesses, as well as all that concerns his art and industry as a painter.

Item the aforesaid testator gives and grants forever to Baptiste de Villanis, his servant, half of a garden outside the walls of Milan, and the other half of this garden to Salay, his servant; in this garden, the aforesaid Salay, has built a house which will be and will always remain in perpetuity to the aforesaid Salay, his heirs and successors, and this as a reward for the good and gracious services that the aforesaid de Villanis and Salay, his servants, have rendered him.

Item the aforesaid Testator gives and grants to Maturine, his servant, a robe of black cloth, lined with hair, a cloak of cloth, and two ducats, all payable at one time, and this in recognition of the good services rendered to him by the aforesaid Maturine.

Item he wants that at his funeral there be sixty candles, which will be carried by sixty poor people, to whom money will be distributed for having carried them; it will be the aforesaid Melzo who will distribute it to them at his will; These candles will be distributed among the four churches above named.

Item the aforesaid testator gives and grants to each church above named, ten pounds of large wax candles which will be placed in the said churches to be used on the day on which the above-mentioned Services are celebrated.

Item that it be given to the poor of the Hospital of God, to the poor of Saint-Lazare d'Amboise, and for this purpose that the sum and quantities of seventy sous tournois be given and paid to the treasurers of these Confraternities.

Item the aforesaid Testator gives and grants to Messire François de Melzo, present and accepting, the remainder of his pension and a sum of money which is a debt of the past, until the day of his death. To receive this, go to the Receiver or Treasurer General, Mr. Jehan

Sapin where the sums of money and the said pension that he will have received are kept. In the event that he dies before the aforesaid testator, this money will be found with the said testator in the place of the above called du Cloux.

In the same way, he gives to the said de Melzo all his clothes that he has here in the place called Le Cloux, as much as a reward for his good services that he has rendered up to now and for his salaries, the fatigues and troubles he may have for the present will, all of course at the expense of the Testator.

He orders and desires that the sum of four hundred crowns of the sun which he has in deposit in the hands of the treasurer of Santa Maria Nuova in the city of Florence be given to his carnal brothers, residing in Florence, the profits which the aforesaid treasurers may owe to the said Testator up to the present in relation to the four hundred crowns, from the day on which the aforesaid testator gave them and consigned them to the said Treasurers.

Item the said Testator wills and orders that the said Francis of Melzo be and remain sole executor of his will and that the said will be revealed to be just and complete, as it is narrated and bound to keep and observe. The aforesaid Leonardo da Vinci, constituted testator, has hereby obligated and binds his heirs and successors of all goods, movable and immovable, present and future, and has hereby renounced all and every provision to the contrary.

Given in the said place of Le Cloux in the presence of Master Esprit Fieri, vicar of the church of Saint-Denis in Amboise, Master Guillaume Croyant, priest and Capuchin, Master Cyprien Fulchiv, Father François de Cortona and François de Milan, Religious of the convent of the Fathers Minor in Amboise, witnesses called and summoned for this purpose by the juror of the said Court, in the presence of the aforesaid Messire François de Melzo, accepting and consenting, who has promised by religion and oath of his body, by him given bodily in our hands, never to do, go, say, or go against it, and has been sealed, at his request, with the royal seal affixed to legal contracts in the city of Amboise as a sign of truth. Dated the xxiii day of April MDXVIII before Easter.

And on the twenty-third of the said month of April, MDXVIII, in the presence of Master Guillaume Boreau, Royal Notary at the Court of the Baillage of Amboise, the aforesaid Leonardo da Vinci gave, by his will and the order of his last wills and testament said above, to the said Baptiste de Villanis, present and accepting, the

right of water which the late good King Louis XII, of happy memory, had given to the said Leonardo da Vinci, on the navigation of the canal of St. Christopher in the Duchy of Milan, as a gratuity, for the said Villanis to always enjoy it in the manner and manner which the said lord himself has done.

Given in the presence of M. François de Melzo, Gentleman of Milan, and in my own.

And, on the aforesaid day of the said month of April of the said year MDXVIII, the aforesaid Leonardo da Vinci, by his will and the order of his last will and testament already said above, gave to the aforesaid Baptiste de Villanis, present and accepting, all and every movable and utensil of his house here in the place of Le Cloux, and this in case the said de Villanis survives the aforesaid Leonardo da Vinci.

Done in the presence of M. François de Melzo and myself, Notary, etc.

Signé: B O R E A U".

This presumed will gives pride of place to Francisco Melzi since the latter is the great beneficiary.

In fact, he was not only appointed executor of his will and received a sum of money concerning a pension that had earned interest, but also and above all "everything that concerns his art and his painting industry". This last expression is sufficiently general and imprecise to encompass the entire pictorial production of the testator...

From all of the above, one can legitimately wonder what really happened.

It must be noted that King Francis 1st never issued Leonardo da Vinci with a letter of naturality, because if this had been the case, we would find traces of it in the exhaustive 9-volume catalogue of the king's acts. It will also be specified that no one has ever found any trace of any request for a letter of naturality than Leonardo da Vinci to the royal power.

Leonardo da Vinci was therefore unable to draw up any will since it presupposed the prior granting of a letter of naturality.

Given the importance of the granting of a letter of naturality issued by François 1st for the supposed will to be legally valid, one can only be surprised by the fact that the notary of Amboise does not expressly mention, in the actual drafting of the supposed will, the date of the letter of naturality to which there is no allusion.

This omission raises the greatest doubts not only

about the existence of a letter of naturality in favour of Leonardo da Vinci, but also and above all about the authenticity of the alleged will.

It is difficult to imagine, in fact, that the notary of Amboise could have ignored the mention of this essential formality which conditioned the validity of the alleged will: no letter of naturality meant no will possible.

The letter from Francisco Melzi to Leonardo da Vinci's brothers dated 15 June 1519, referring to the existence of a letter of naturality and the existence of a will, therefore contains information that is manifestly inaccurate, or even false, which may have deceived some historians who have taken up the information without verifying it.

In the absence of any originals that have never been found, the translation of the copy of the supposed will discovered in an incredible way in a barrel has no probative value.

The fable put together by Francisco Melzi does not hold water.

It is more than likely that the real course of events is completely different.

The real course of events

The chronology of the facts is, in all likelihood, very simple:

Leonardo da Vinci died on 2 May 1519.

Having been born abroad, his property, and in particular the Mona Lisa, reverted to the king in the absence of a letter of naturality and by virtue of the right of windfall.

His disciple and assistant Francisco Melzi got his hands on several other paintings and drawings in the painter's studio.

A few years later, wanting to sell the said paintings and drawings, he could not justify their legal origin and fabricated both the letter of 15 June 1519 (which is doubtful that it was really sent to the painter's brothers) and the will of 23 April 1519, both of which were apocryphal in nature.

In his article already cited, the historian Bertrand Jestaz specifies that the discovery, in 1991, of an inventory drawn up in Milan on April 21, 1525 after

the death of Salai, the other disciple of Leonardo da Vinci, for the division of his property, may have led us to believe that Francis I would have bought paintings, including the Mona Lisa, from the artist in 1518, before his death. But this inventory does not mention the name of Leonardo da Vinci at all, and is limited to a pithy enumeration of paintings which can in no serious way be linked to the artist. This is pure conjecture based on uncertain extrapolations.

This is so true that in the notice of the work on the Louvre Museum's collections website, the painting is presented as "*most probably acquired by François 1er in 1518*"⁹

According to the Louvre Museum itself, the acquisition by François 1er, which is based on the above-mentioned inventory discovered in 1991, is only probable, but by no means established.

Bertrand Jestaz even thinks it useful to specify in his above-mentioned article:

"It was therefore necessary to give up the idea that Leonardo would have left any paintings to Francis I during his lifetime, because even if it had been an earlier manual gift, he would certainly have confirmed it in his will in order to avoid any possible dispute and to clarify for his heirs and his executor the devolution of his property. The masterpieces had vanished and left no trace before resurfacing later in the royal collection, which appeared to be a particularly powerful magic trick."

In the absence of proof of a letter of naturality, in the absence of any trace in the archives of verification and registration of such a letter with the Chamber of Accounts and the Chamber of the Treasury, in the absence of any deed of sale or donation, it is clear that in reality François 1er never acquired the Mona Lisa for hard cash (or by donation) before the death of the artist, but appropriated the work by making use of the right of windfall, then applicable by operation of law for foreigners.

Indeed, it could not be otherwise in law, the right of windfall being at the time a matter of public order, except in the case of a letter of naturality.

The right of windfall

Ancient Rome had a regime characteristic of the

(<https://collections.louvre.fr>).

⁹ Note The Mona Lisa on the Louvre Museum collections website – See paragraph on the history of the work

ancient city: anyone who did not belong to it was considered a pilgrim. However, this conception was only logical as long as the boundaries of the Roman state were merged with those of the Urbs. From the moment they passed them, the inhabitants of the conquered countries, Italians first, then provincials, were no longer real foreigners.

In 212, the Emperor Caracalla issued an edict in these terms¹⁰ :

"I grant Roman citizenship to all foreigners domiciled on the territory of the empire..."

Like all Roman citizens, foreigners (called "peregrines") could now freely transfer their property to their heirs in return for an inheritance tax of 10%.

This provision was taken up by the Code of Theodosius in 438.

The barbarian invasions led to the fall of the Western Roman Empire around 476.

From this time on, there was a slow regression in the application of Roman law, particularly in Gaul, with an absence of rights for foreigners.

The feudal period that followed it (between the ninth and thirteenth centuries) marked an important change.

A custom gradually took hold according to which was a foreigner:

- 1- the one who was born in France and who belonged to a castle other than the one where he is now
- 2 - the one who was born outside France

The former are called "aubains", the latter are "wrecks".

This situation is studied at great length in the doctoral thesis of Maître Christo Bracaloff, lawyer¹¹.

He explains that:

"The word aubain appears for the first time in the ninth century, precisely at the time when the feudal system had just been established in France. It is therefore natural that this word should be connected with the system in which it was born. Now, this system can be summed up in this: the lord who lives in the feudal castle is a small absolute sovereign; it is towards him that everything converges, for him that the sun shines and the earth produces. He enjoys his power; he is absolute master over his lands; he can make war, mint

money, establish taxes, administer justice, in short, do whatever he wants within the limits of his domains. Among its various rights there is one, and almost the most important, and that is the ban, that is to say, the right of jurisdiction over the whole extent of its territory, a right which marked the extent of the seigneurial power. All those who were not of his ban, under his jurisdiction, were "alii banished", that is to say, people who were not of his ban, or otherwise called "aubains". The condition of foreigners of the first class, that is to say, of those who had left one castellany to settle in another, was almost the same as that of the serfs of the lord, provided that they had recognized the lord within a year and a day. A first difference existed that the stranger must, on his death, leave in his will, to the lord whom he had acknowledged, a new purse and four deniers, on pain of a fine of sixty sols.

Here is what we find in the custom of Laudunois, under the title of Middle Justice article 5: "When no fairground who is not of the diocese dies in his justice, the lord has the right to have the aubinage: that is to say, a new purse and four deniers in it; and the said aubinage must be paid to the lord his receiver, or in his absence, to another his officer, before the body of the deceased is put out of the house where he died; and in default of paying the said aubinage, the said lord may take and levy sixty sols of fine on the heirs and goods of the said deceased, together with his said aubinage".

Thus, in feudal times, the right of windfall, as in Roman law, was limited to a relatively modest tax to which the inheritances of foreigners were subject.

The principle was that foreigners could freely transfer their property to their heirs provided that they paid the aubinage. However, everything changed during the transition from the feudal era to the monarchical era. With royal centralization, the cities and lords lost their prerogatives in terms of "naturalization" to the benefit of the king: only he could grant it, since he was the sole holder of the right of windfall, the naturalization of which had the effect of relieving the foreigner.

In his above-mentioned doctoral thesis, Mr. Bracaloff indicates on page 76 that "we believe, however, that we can fix the time of the beginning of this period at the publication of the establishments of

droit french", thesis defended in 1884 before the Faculty of Law of Aix. National Library of France.

¹⁰ "Papyrus Giessen 40" kept in the Giessen Museum in Germany).

¹¹ "De la condition des étrangers en droit romain et en

Saint Louis, because it is then that we see the appearance of a new principle in which we find the explanation of the change in the present legislation. The main object of the establishments of St. Louis was to transform the seigniorial right over the aliens into a sovereign right and to do away with the distinction between the aliens born outside France and those born there; for, vis-à-vis the king, the latter could only be French...

Royalty, weak at the beginning, ended by imposing itself in such a way that at the end of the sixteenth century there was no longer any discussion on the point of knowing whether the right of windfall was a royal right."

The Establishments of Saint Louis are a legal compilation composed between All Saints' Day 1272 and June 19, 1273, and therefore falsely attributed to King Louis IX (died in August 1270). Written by a jurist from Orléans (and of a private order), they are organized into two books and based on the custom of Orléans and Paris, as well as the ordinances of Saint Louis.

This text was published by Du Cange, in 1668, as an appendix to his edition of Jean de Joinville's History of Saint Louis; by Eusèbe de Laurière, in 1723, in the collection of the Ordinances; by François Jérôme Riffard de Saint-Martin (1744-1814), in 1786, with a modern language version; by Paul Violet in 1881 in the collection of the Société de l'histoire de France. In Paul Violet's edition, we find¹² the following rule, written in Old French:

"Se no aubans ou batarz muert sanz oir ou sanz lignage, li rois est oirs, ou li sires souz cui il est, si il muert ou cuer de son chastel. Ne nus batarz, ne aubains ne puet faire autre seignor que le roi en obeissance, né en autre seignorie, né en son resort, qui valir, ne qui est estable, selon lonc le usage d'Orlenois et de Sedistante".

The translation into modern French is as follows:

"If a godsend or a bastard dies without heirs or descendants, the king is his heir, or the lord whose man he is, if he dies a serf. But a bastard or a bargain cannot take any lord but the king in the territories that obey him directly, nor let him establish himself in other lordships which are the jurisdiction of his justice, according to the

custom of Orleans and Sologne."

In an ordinance dated 21 April 1475¹³ and entitled "*Letters to exempt from the right of windfall the sums due to Conrart Hanequis and Pierre Scheffre*", of Mainz, printers, King Louis XI was led to enact a general law of the kingdom concerning the right of windfall.

The procedure may be surprising today since it is on the occasion of a letter of exemption concerning two natural persons that the king is led, incidentally, but expressly, to take a general and impersonal provision.

In his ordinance of 21 April 1475, King Louis XI thus enshrined "*erga omnes*" the rule according to which: "*By the general law of our kingdom, whenever no foreigner and non-native of our kingdom goes from life trespasse, without letters of naturality and authorization and power of us to testify, all the goods that he has in our kingdom, at the time of his said trespas, we competent and belong by right of aubénage*"

The translation into modern French is as follows:

"By the general law of our kingdom, whenever a foreigner who is not a native of our kingdom goes from life to death, without letters of naturality and authorization by us to be able to testify, all the property that he has in our said kingdom at the hour of his death is within our jurisdiction and belongs to us by right of windfall."

It follows that all foreigners who die without a letter of naturality see their property located in France revert by right to the king. All foreigners are thus subject to a total incapacity for testamentary and inheritance matters.

From a particular law that did not recognize the incapacity of inheritance and will, we move on to a common law from which no one escapes, described by Louis XI in his above-mentioned ordinance of 21 April 1475 as the "*general law of the kingdom*".

Successively, the feudal term applied to persons was transformed into a modern term designating property and, soon, a general law applicable to the latter and enforceable against their owners.

The phenomenon reflects the culmination of the process by which the sovereign achieved the gradual

¹² "Les Etablissements de Saint Louis" accompanied by primitive texts and derivative texts by Paul Violet volume II page 428 – Published by the Renouard bookshop 1831

¹³ Ordinances of the Kings of France of the Third Race – Imprimerie Royale – Volume XVIII page 114 – Bibliothèque Nationale de France

absorption of the old feudal legal regime applied to the aubain.

The unlawful nature of the appropriation by François 1er of the painting The Mona Lisa under the right of windfall and the non-existence of the contested act

We have seen that the only legal and public policy way in which King Francis I was able to come into possession of the disputed painting was the exercise of the right of windfall.

Indeed, when Leonardo da Vinci died on May 2, 1519, in the absence of a letter of naturality and faced with the legal impossibility of transmitting his property to his heirs (his siblings domiciled in Tuscany) in his will, all of his patrimony belonged to the king by right.

The questionable nature of François 1er's appropriation of the painting The Mona Lisa under the right of windfall is not in doubt both with regard to the law applicable at the time of the facts and to contemporary positive law.

I shall therefore consider in turn the illegality of the contested act on these two temporal aspects.

We will also answer the question of whether Francis I had the right, at the time of the facts, to legally appropriate the painting The Mona Lisa belonging to Leonardo da Vinci under the right of windfall. We will also consider whether the illegality of such an appropriation is of such gravity that it renders the appropriation decision non-existent.

The illegality of the appropriation of the Mona Lisa under the applicable law

At the time of the facts, the right of windfall was legally based on the ordinance of King Louis XI of 21 April 1475. In so far as it infringed on the right of property, this right of windfall was a practice that was totally contrary to natural law. But the contested act continues to produce its effects today since the Mona Lisa is part of the collections of the Louvre Museum and is the subject of a public exhibition, even though because of its illegal appropriation it should be the property of the

descendants of Leonardo da Vinci's heirs. It will therefore be necessary to establish how this appropriation also contravenes contemporary positive law.

The infringement of natural law

Natural law or jusnaturalism is a mode of legal thought that is opposed to positive law, to positivism. Therefore, here, the law is not what is laid down by the authority empowered to do so, but the natural law happens to be, according to Serge Braudo (honorary advisor to the Versailles Court of Appeal):

"The set of rights that each individual possesses because of his belonging to humanity and not because of the society in which he lives. Natural law, which includes the right to life and health, the right to liberty, such as the right to property; it is inherent in humanity, universal and unalterable"¹⁴

"Natural law, imprescriptible right, sacred right" is how the Constituent Assembly of 1789, in the wake of the various American declarations of rights, had described property. Reading the discussions surrounding the preparation of the Code in 1804, especially the introductory speeches, one often has the feeling that its drafters intended to implement this principle, and that they are guided by the thought that led to its adoption.

It is the mutualized principle of the right of conservation which must nevertheless be accommodated by total respect for individual property. This right, being founded in nature, justifies that any individual who enters society with his property must benefit from the appropriate protection by the normative power, having this protection taken into account by civil law.

Thus, by appropriating the Mona Lisa, by using the right of windfall to the detriment of Leonardo da Vinci's legitimate heirs, King Francis 1st did not respect the natural law to which he was bound.

This natural law was imposed on him and constituted a norm which he was obliged to follow and which he manifestly violated.

¹⁴ "Legal Dictionary of Private Law" by Serge Braudot (online publication on the internet

The violation of positive law and the unconstitutional nature of the ordinance of 21 April 1475

The appropriation of the disputed painting continues to produce its effects today since the Mona Lisa is part of the collections of the Louvre Museum and is the subject of a public exhibition, even though because of its illegal appropriation it should be the property of the descendants of Leonardo da Vinci's heirs.

We are therefore in the presence of a continuous illegality that has been perpetuated from the origin of the appropriation to the present day.

The right of windfall, officially enshrined as the general law of the kingdom by the ordinance of King Louis XI of 21 April 1475, was abolished by the National Constituent Assembly during the Revolution.

In its session of August 6, 1790, Barrère de Vieuzac, rapporteur on the abolition of the right of windfall, wrote¹⁵ :

"This feudal custom, as contrary to humanity as to the law of nations, disappeared when the kings regained some authority; and the wise establishments of St. Louis stipulate that foreigners shall be able to make no other lord than the king. From then on, the right of windfall was regarded as state-owned and incommunicable.

Legislation came to legitimize what had been, among the ancients, only a proof of ignorance; among the feudal lords, only an act of usurpation; and in our country, only a fiscal police which has since undergone some vicissitudes and some softening of the voice of commerce, the sciences and the arts. These are the principles observed up to this time in this matter: every foreigner is capable, in a kingdom, of the law of nations; he can freely sell, exchange and, in general, enter into all kinds of contracts that this right authorizes; he may give and receive inter vivos, but he may not receive or dispose of by will or by death. He lives free, but he dies a serf: such is the atrocious maxim which the

representatives of a free people must hasten to erase from its laws. France must open her bosom today to all the peoples of the earth. What motives could oppose it, politics? But this right has appeared so barbarous, and contrary even to the interests of the State, that our ancient laws have softened or suspended its exercise. Let the foreigner come to France to seek a homeland; that he may reside there, without fear of seeing legitimate heirs deprived of a property which should naturally belong to them; that he may enjoy liberty there during his life, and his children of his beneficence after his death."

Article 4 of the decree of 13 April 1791 enshrined in its article 7: *"The rights of escheat, windfall, bastardy, wrecks, kelp, found treasure, and that of appropriating vain and vague lands, or gastes, moors, heme or vacant property, garrigues, flégards or vareschaix, shall no longer take place in favour of the former lords, as from the publication of the decrees of 4 August 1789, the former lords remaining, since that time, relieved of the maintenance of foundlings"*¹⁶

However, under the First Empire, Articles 726 and 912 of the Civil Code reintroduced an important distinction between nationals and foreigners with regard to the law of succession.

They made the right for foreigners to receive an inheritance in France subject to conditions of diplomatic and legislative reciprocity: the foreigner could inherit in France only under the same conditions as a French person could inherit in the country of which the foreigner was a national.

Re-established in the Civil Code of 1803, the right of windfall was definitively abolished by Article 1 of Law No. 6986 of 14 July 1819, which was worded as follows¹⁷:

"Louis, by the grace of God, KING OF FRANCE AND NAVARRE, to all present and to come, GREETINGS.

We have moved, the Houses have adopted, WE HAVE ORDERED AND DO ORDER the following:

Article 1: Articles 726 and 912 of the Civil Code are repealed: consequently, foreigners shall have the right to inherit, dispose of and receive in the same manner as

¹⁵ Report on the abolition of the right of windfall, at the session of August 6, 1790. In: Parliamentary Archives from 1787 to 1860 - First series (1787-1799) Volume XVII - From 9 July to 12 August 1790. Paris: Librairie administrative P. Dupont, 1884. pp. 628-629

¹⁶ Corrected text of the decree on feudal rights, at the session of April 13, 1791. In: Parliamentary Archives from

1787 to 1860 - First series (1787-1799) Volume XXV - From 13 April 1791 to 11 May 1791. Paris: Librairie administrative P. Dupont, 1886. pp. 4-10

¹⁷ Law published on the légifrance website <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>

French nationals throughout the Kingdom.

The law of 14 July 1819 had as its object the repeal of these articles of the Civil Code. It did not, therefore, strictly speaking, abolish the right of windfall, which had already been abolished in 1791, but the conditions of reciprocity to which the inheritance of foreigners in France was subject.

Nevertheless, Article 2 of the same law maintained, in part, a condition of legislative reciprocity since it provided that *"in the case of the division of the same estate between foreign and French co-heirs, the latter shall levy on the property located in France a portion equal to the value of the property located in a foreign country from which they would be excluded, in any capacity, by virtue of local laws and customs"*.

This provision applied until Decision No. 2011-159 QPC of 5 August 2011 of the Constitutional Council, which declared it unconstitutional and, in particular, contrary to the principle of equality¹⁸.

Indeed, the above-mentioned decision of the Constitutional Council of 5 August 2011 recalls without any ambiguity the principle of equality and the right to property, which are clearly contravened by the right of windfall.

No one can seriously dispute that the right of windfall constitutes a manifest violation of Article 17 of the Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen of 26 August 1789 (which has constitutional value since it is expressly referred to in the preamble to the Constitution of 4 October 1958) according to which *"property being an inviolable and sacred right, no one can be deprived of it, except when public necessity, legally established, obviously requires it, and on the condition of fair and prior compensation"*.

The right of windfall also contravenes the principle of equality enshrined in article 1 of the above-mentioned Declaration, according to which *"Men are born and remain free and equal in rights"*.

The right of windfall is also a clear violation of Article 17 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 10 December 1948, which states that *"everyone, whether alone or in community, has the right to property. No one may be arbitrarily deprived of his property."*

In addition, according to Article 1 of the First Additional Protocol to the European Convention for

the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms: *"Every natural or legal person has the right to the peaceful enjoyment of his property. No one may be deprived of his property except in the public interest and under the conditions provided for by law and the general principles of international law."*

In the light of the above, the question arises of the constitutionality of the royal ordinance of 21 April 1475, the legal basis and general law of the kingdom on the basis of which King Francis 1st appropriated the Mona Lisa by asserting the right of windfall, the consequences of which continue today.

It should be noted in this regard that a priority question of constitutionality may be filed against any law, regardless of its date of promulgation, including if it predates the Constitution of 4 October 1958, the founding text of the Fifth Republic. It may therefore relate to very old texts, such as a text adopted by the National Convention or a royal ordinance.

The non-existence of the act of appropriation

It is clear that the painting The Mona Lisa was the subject of an appropriation tainted by a marked excess of power.

A deed obtained by fraud does not create rights (CE 29 November 2002, req. 223027). This is the application of the adage *"Fraus omnia corrumpit"*.

In its famous Assembly decision of 31 May 1957 (application no. 26188), the Council of State ruled that *"administrative acts affected by a particularly serious and flagrant illegality must be regarded as non-existent and are considered null and void"*.

The non-existent act is so intolerable that the judge only notes it. If the judge annulled it, it would assume that the act was at one time presumed to be legal.

It has virtually never seen the light of day.

The qualification of a non-existent act does not meet very precise criteria. Indeed, the administrative judge uses a rather general formula which is as follows:

"An act can only be considered non-existent if it is devoid of material existence or if it is vitiated by a defect of such gravity that it affects not only its legality, but its very existence" (for example: CE, 28 Sept. 2016, req. n° 399173, ANTICOR).

¹⁸ Decision published on the website of the Constitutional Council <https://www.conseil-constitutionnel.fr>

This formula reveals two main categories of non-existent acts:

- Material non-existence
- the particularly serious defect tainting an act that is already illegal by nature

A non-existent act produces two sets of effects: it can be nullified at any time and it produces no legal effect. When an act that is in fact non-existent comes before the administrative judge, the latter must raise it ex officio as a means of public policy (for example: CE, 5 May 1971, application no. 75655, Prefect of Paris).

The non-existent act does not create any acquired rights. In other words, it is not possible to raise anything on the basis of such an act. The finding or withdrawal of a non-existent act leads to the disappearance of subsequent acts, i.e. those that were taken on the basis of it.

In the present case, the appropriation of the painting The Mona Lisa by means of the right of windfall in the absence of a letter of naturality or a valid deed of sale or gift, to the detriment of the artist's heirs, constitutes an act of particularly serious illegality.

Therefore, the incorporation of this table into the public domain is manifestly non-existent.

In law, such incorporation is legally non-existent and null and void, as Articles L451-3 and L451-5 of the Heritage Code and Article L3111-1 of the General Code of the Property of Public Persons, which enshrine the imprescriptibility and inalienability of public collections, being unenforceable in the event of non-existence. In addition, Article D451-19 of the Heritage Code provides that the removal of an item from an inventory of the museums of France may occur "*in the event of undue registration on the inventory*".

The appropriation of a painting under the guise of a windfall right contrary to the most elementary principles of law and its conservation by the Louvre Museum amounts to a substantial infringement of the right to property. The non-existent act does not create any acquired right. In other words, it is not possible to raise anything on the basis of such an act. The finding or withdrawal of a non-existent act leads

to the disappearance of subsequent acts, i.e. those that were taken on the basis of it.

The descendants of Leonardo da Vinci's heirs

Two Italian historians, Alessandro Vezzosi and Agnese Sabato, have discovered at least 14 living direct descendants of Leonardo da Vinci.

These 14 direct descendants are in fact from the lineages of his brothers and sisters, the artist never having had children. Their investigation, which dates from 2021 published in the journal Human Evolution and relayed by the British daily The Guardian¹⁹, reveals that the 14 descendants are between 1 and 85 years old and live in Tuscany, Leonardo da Vinci's native Italian region. The two researchers conducted DNA analysis, in addition to dissecting a 690-year-old genealogical line, through church records and land records in the area.

No less than 21 generations are involved, from 1331, the year of his grandfather's birth, to the present day. They include five family branches. Leonardo da Vinci had 22 half-brothers. To reach their results, the researchers tracked the Y chromosome, passed down from father to son, which remained almost unchanged for 25 generations, Vezzosi told the Italian news agency Ansa.

It is clear that there are direct descendants of Leonardo da Vinci, some of whom have not been identified, only 14 of them having been found by the above-mentioned investigation, without their names having been revealed.

The Mona Lisa actually belongs to these heirs insofar as the initial act of appropriation by François 1st under the guise of the right of windfall is legally non-existent and could not have produced any effect.

The referral to the Council of State by the NGO International Restitutions

It is in this context that the NGO International Restitutions filed a request with the Council of State on February 16, 2024.

The statutory purpose²⁰ of this association,

¹⁹ *The New Genealogical Tree of the Da Vinci Family for Leonardo's DNA. Ancestors and descendants in direct male line down to the present XXI generation* – Published in Human Evolution volume 36, 2021 - See also the article

"Two historians present Leonardo Da Vinci's family tree" published in the magazine Sciences et Avenir on July 7, 2021.

²⁰ Official Journal of the French Republic of 14 February

governed by the French law of 1 July 1901, is as follows:

- (a) to ensure the lawfulness of the composition of the collections of public museums;
- (b) to protect movable cultural heritage so that it remains available to indigenous peoples in the place or country of origin of creation in such a way as to preserve, affirm and promote their cultural identity and the creative power of their history;
- (c) obtain, with a view to achieving the objective set out in points (a) and (b), the annulment or declaration of the non-existence of any act which has led to the incorporation or assignment in the public domain of any museum or establishment, whether French or foreign, of any cultural property which has been looted, acquired or appropriated fraudulently, irregularly or illegitimately directly or indirectly, both by private persons and by States or legal persons governed by public law, in particular, but not exclusively, on the occasion of the various periods of armed conflict or colonization

The purpose of the application filed before the Council of State was to:

- "to declare non-existent the decision of illicit spoliation taken by King Francis 1st concerning the Mona Lisa*
- consequently declare non-existent all subsequent acts taken on the basis of the contested decision*
- to order that the lawfulness of the composition of the collections of the Louvre Museum be re-established in so far as they include the above-mentioned portrait*
- order, in respect of the business management carried out by the applicant on behalf of the descendants of the painter's heirs, the removal from the inventory of the Louvre Museum of the above-mentioned portrait for undue inscription pursuant to Article D451-19 of the Heritage Code*
- to refer any interested party to appeal as he sees fit so that a decision can be made by the judicial judge on the devolution of the above-mentioned portrait"*

In a separate brief from the appeal on the merits, the NGO International Restitutions also filed a priority question of constitutionality concerning the royal ordinance of 21 April 1475.

In limine litis, the question of the admissibility of the application arose before the judge.

In a previous appeal²¹, concerning the removal from

the Louvre Museum's inventory of works looted during the sack of the Summer Palace in Beijing in 1860, the NGO International Restitutions had seen its request declared inadmissible on the grounds that only the owners of the works had an interest in taking action.

The same question of admissibility had to be decided by the Council of State on the occasion of the second appeal concerning the Mona Lisa

The decision issued by the Council of State on May 14, 2024

In order to avoid a second inadmissibility decision without the merits of the case being examined, the NGO International Restitutions intervened in the case as part of the case management.

Business management is defined in Article 1301 of the Civil Code as *"the person who, without being required to do so, knowingly and usefully manages the business of another, without the knowledge or opposition of the master of this business"*. In other words, it is a question of a person, who is called the business manager, spontaneously intervening in the affairs of another, the owner of the business or the managed, in order to render him a service. The particularity of business management is that it assumes that a person has acted on behalf of a third party and in his or her interest, without having been mandated by the third party, or that he or she has been kept informed.

In a decision of 21 December 1981,²² the Court of Cassation ruled that a person who is not a representative may, due to exceptional circumstances, represent a third party in court by acting as a business manager.

In support of its decision, it specifies that *"no legal provision makes the validity of the action brought by the business manager subject to the acceptance of the proceedings by the third party against whom this action is brought"*.

It is clear from this decision that there is therefore nothing to prevent legal action from being brought by the business manager on behalf of the master, as long as it is a question of representing another person and not acting in his own name, since no one

2023 - Announcement n°1361

²¹ Judgment of the Council of State No. 463108 of 23

November 2022

²² Cassation, civil 1, 21 December 1981, 80-15.854

pleads by attorney.

In the present case, there are descendants of Leonardo da Vinci's heirs who are the legitimate owners of the painting wrongly inscribed in the inventory of the Louvre Museum. These descendants have not all been identified to date. The NGO International Restitutions considered that it was therefore in its interest to take action to request, in the context of the management of cases, the requested removal, in particular on behalf of the unidentified heirs of Leonardo da Vinci's descendants.

In its decision no. 491862 of May 14, 2024, the judges of the Council of State did not validate the legal analysis of the NGO International Restitutions and fully followed the conclusions of the public rapporteur who was in favor of an inadmissibility of the request for lack of interest in acting.

The decision of the Council of State is motivated as follows:

"In the first place, the fact that the International Restitutions association has set itself the statutory object of "ensuring the lawfulness of the composition of the collections of public museums" and "protecting the movable cultural heritage so that it remains available to the indigenous populations in the place or country of origin of creation in such a way as to preserve, affirm and promote their cultural identity and the creative power of their history" is not such as to confer on it an interest giving it standing to bring before the court of excess of power an action to contest the belonging of property to the movable public domain of the State in order to allow the restitution of such property to persons whom it claims to be the legitimate owners, only the latter having an interest, if necessary, in bringing legal action to obtain the restitution of these assets. Nor can the association maintain that it is intended to represent these persons in the context of "business management". The application of the association "International Restitutions" is therefore, on this first ground, manifestly inadmissible.

Secondly, claims seeking a declaration by the administrative judge of "decisions" by which, under the Ancien Régime, the sovereign authority would have acquired and incorporated property in the domain of the Crown, property which is now part of the public domain, are manifestly inadmissible. Such is the case with the claims directed against the alleged decision by which, according to the applicant association, King

Francis I appropriated the portrait of the Mona Lisa in 1519.

It follows from the foregoing that the application of the International Restitutions association is vitiated by manifest inadmissibility which cannot be covered in the course of the proceedings and must be rejected pursuant to the provisions of Article R. 351-4 of the Code of Administrative Justice, including its claims seeking the annulment as a consequence of the acts allegedly taken on the basis of the "decision" of 1519, as well as its submissions for the purposes of an injunction, without it being necessary to rule on the referral to the Constitutional Council of the priority question of constitutionality raised by the association alleging that the provisions of the Ordinance of 21 April 1475 infringe the rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution.

Under Article R. 741-12 of the Code of Administrative Justice: "The judge may impose on the author of an application that he considers abusive a fine of not more than 10,000 euros". In the present case, the present application of the International Restitutions association is abusive. Therefore, it should be ordered to pay a fine of 3,000 euros."

It will simply be observed that this judgment is insufficiently reasoned in that it concisely dismisses the interest of the NGO International Restitutions in bringing proceedings in respect of the management of cases, without explaining, even summarily, how such management does not apply in the present case.

In the Van de Hurk v. Netherlands judgment of 19 April 1994, the European Court of Human Rights held that "Article 6-1 of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms obliges the courts to give reasons for their decisions".

The European Court of Human Rights verifies the existence of the statement of reasons and considers that it cannot be totally absent from a decision. It also ensures that it is sufficient: it then rejects the implicit nature of the reasoning and asserts that it cannot take on a concise aspect.

In these circumstances, the NGO International Restitutions has lodged an application with the European Court of Human Rights for violation of the right to a fair trial enshrined in Article 6-1 of the Convention.

This request is currently under investigation.

Interim conclusion

The Council of State admits *that "only the legitimate owners have an interest in bringing legal action to obtain restitution"*.

The ball is now in the court of Leonardo da Vinci's heirs who will be able, if they wish, to take the matter to court to decide the question of the legitimacy of the appropriation of the Mona Lisa by Francis 1st.

The decision of the Council of State was nevertheless predictable insofar as it would have been very naïve to expect that the wise men of the Royal Palace, whose Jacobinism is well known, would order the return to Italy of the most emblematic painting in the Louvre Museum.

However, we can regret a poorly crafted decision on admissibility and a gesture of annoyance *"ab irato"* in the pronouncement of a fine of 3000 € for a procedure qualified as abusive, again without the slightest motivation justifying the abusive nature of the request, admittedly atypical, initiated by the NGO International Restitutions.

Given the media impact that this decision of the Council of State has generated in both the national and international press, particularly in Italy (several thousand articles in 87 different countries), this case may not be completely closed.

The future will tell.
